

Alternative Agriculture in Maro, Spain

Intro and Aims

Alternative agriculture is an increasingly important part of rural life in drought affected southern Spain. Water availability and land rights are changing so farmers of Maro have adapted to a different demand. By planting crops like flowers which demand less in resources, space, and management, farmers become more efficient. This will be done through:

- Investigating key differences in crops changes through their life cycles
- Using interviews, pictures, and observations to understand these differences

Methods

During the day we conducted a series of interviews and walking tours of farmers' respective plots, and other related areas, while taking note of our findings. Therefore, our main methods were:

- Interviews
- Observations
- Pictures

Figure 1: Map of Maro. Source: OpenStreetMaps

Seed

The seed starters used are common, commercialized varieties, and can be planted very compactly, a necessary trait when nearly all farmers rent their land. Higher growing trees and vines, like past crops used here, require more growing room, and as a result more land. These past crops have been in Spain for centuries since the Muslims first introduced them in the 12th century (Nizamoglu, 2006). Additionally, tomato seeds will not effectively grow in temperatures above 25C (Labouriau and Osborn, 1984), but Spain exhibits these temperatures and higher during May through to October. Meanwhile, Marigold, one common alternative, in fact grows better at temperatures of 30C versus 20C (van Iersel and Seymour, 2003).

Figure 2: Seedlings of one Maro farmer. Source: Author

Compost

Unharvested plant parts are composted, reducing the cost of new soils, and need for pesticides and fertilizers. This also reintroduces carbon into the soil after it has been depleted from bimonthly harvesting and disruption of soils (Zheng et al., 2020). This carbon rich soil is additionally helpful, as it fills in the gaps of ecofriendly sprays. Since some of these flowers are edible, farmers are limited in what fertilizers or pesticides can be used.

Figure 6: Compost in Maro. Source: Author

Figure 3: Water tanks of Maro. Source: Author

Water and Irrigation

Lack of water due to the drought is often blamed on farmers overconsumption of their limited spring sourced water. Farmers use water tanks, large concrete cylinders, to store large amounts of water, due to the weekly water usage cycling. This area, is used to a regular water supply allowing for more water intensive crops but has relied on alternatives since droughts have dried up the spring. The irrigation of water using channels to transport from spring to farm is also a Muslim invention brought over during the 12 century (Nizamoglu, 2006).

Figure 4: Marigolds of Maro. Source: Author

Package and Sell

Figure 5: Flower parts to sell. Source: Author

Plant parts like the leaves and flowers are harvested and packed into containers and then coolers. They are sent internationally with one major importer, Denmark, purchasing the edible and non-edible varieties. They are used in restaurants for decoration on tables and on plates in the case of the edible varieties. The farmers in this area who still grow tomatoes and fruits etc., rely on a local co-op to package and sell their produce. But due to crop seasonality, they are experiencing hardships, and not sure if they will make it to the end of the year.

Maturity

The harvest rotation for most of these flower varieties is 2 months allowing up to 6 harvests a year. They can be grown year-round, protected by 'invernaderos' during the winter. Whereas past crops like tomatoes, peppers, avocado and fruits are only harvestable during one season in the year. Flowers as an alternative crop require less land for a similar or higher yield. They also require the same amount of water as such past crops but offer a higher profit. Additionally, these dimensionally smaller crops allow for more compact growing areas. A necessary trait for the 'minifundias', Maro's characteristically smaller farms of 2-4 hectares.

Conclusions

The limitations in land-use for Maro farmers, in addition to recent drought patterns drying up the only spring and natural water source for Maro, bring changes. To adapt to such changes, many farmers have turned to alternative agriculture, leaving their historic roots in crops like tomatoes, avocados and fruits. Instead, they determine that a more compact, less land dependent, more water efficient, and more profitable crop is better. Even as the only Spanish Mediterranean town to remain undeveloped, rural life in Maro of southern Spain has still been changing.

References

- Labouriau, L. and Osborn, J. (1984). Temperature Dependence of the Germination of Tomato Seeds. *Journal of Thermal Biology*, [online] 9(4). Available at: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/030645658490010X> [Accessed 18 Mar. 2024].
- Nizamoglu, C. (2006). *Muslim Contribution to Spanish Agriculture*. [online] Muslim Heritage. Available at: <http://muslimheritage.com/muslim-contribution-spanish-agriculture/> [Accessed 18 Mar. 2024].
- van Iersel, M. and Seymour, L. (2003). *Temperature Effects on Photosynthesis, Growth Respiration, and Maintenance Respiration of Marigold*. [online] www.actahort.org. Available at: https://www.actahort.org/books/624/624_76.htm [Accessed 19 Mar. 2024].
- Zheng, X., Aborisade, M.A., Liu, S., Lu, S., Oba, B.T., Xu, X., Cheng, X., He, M., Song, Y. and Ding, H. (2020). The History and Prediction of Composting technology: a Patent Mining. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, [online] 276(1), p.124232. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.124232>.